

Text Mining Techniques for Automated Resume Analysis

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Abstract—Resume parser is a technology used to extract and examine data from the resumes of job applicants. This project aims to automate resume screening, making it quicker and more effective for recruiters and HR departments. The method for generating similarity scores between a resume and a job description using natural language processing techniques is presented in the study. Using CountVectorizer and cosine_similarity, the method entails extracting text from uploaded files, including the education and skills sections of the résumé, and determining similarity scores. The education and skills parts are additionally categorized using a Support Vector Classification model based on similarity scores. This approach may be helpful in the world of human resources and can help match people to job opportunities.

Keywords—resume parser, Natural Language Processing, Cosine similarity function, Support Vector Classification, CountVectorizer, scikit-learn library

I. INTRODUCTION

The task of resume screening and candidate matching is an important process for HR departments and recruiters in finding the right candidate for a job opening. However, manual screening of resumes and job descriptions is a time-consuming and labor-intensive task. To overcome this challenge, automated resume parsing and analysis can be used to improve the efficiency and accuracy of this process. This paper presents a method for automating the process of resume screening in the field of human resources. The proposed approach involves using natural language processing techniques to calculate similarity scores between a job description and a resume. Specifically, the method involves extracting text from uploaded files, including education and skills sections from the resume, and calculating similarity scores using CountVectorizer and cosine_similarity. A Support Vector Classification model is also created to classify the education and skills sections based on their similarity scores. The paper demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed approach through the implementation of a resume parser tool, which can assist in matching candidates to job positions and improve the efficiency of the recruitment process.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mr. Ramraj S, Dr.V.Sivakumar, Kaushik Ramnath G [1]. In this paper, term frequency-inverse document frequency with machine learning and convolution neural network are used to construct an automatic text categorization system for

job recruiting. The goal is to use resumes to classify job seekers into various employment groups. Domain adaptation was utilised because resume data is so delicate. An extensive dataset of job description excerpts was utilised to train a classifier, which was subsequently used to the classification of resume data. SVM, Naive Bayes, and TFIDF were just a few of the algorithms that were used singly and later in an ensemble with another algorithm. To determine the most efficient strategy, the results were compared. The system architecture presented in this study shows the workflow of the resume categorization system as well as how the dataset is created. The data set was created via web scraping real-time resume information of applicants from LinkedIn. Finally, the paper suggests that their system can generate subcategory results that are the best in class.

Suzhi Zhang, Xiaoni Chen [2]. The paper to increase classification accuracy and decrease duplication, the study suggests a modification to the C4.5 decision tree method. The suggested approach is based on cosine similarity and sample selection. First, samples from the data set are chosen using a statistical optimum sample size algorithm in order to determine the optimal sample size. The information gain rate of the combined attribute is then calculated after searching for potential similarity characteristics and combining them based on cosine similarity within the threshold range. In order to construct a decision tree, the optimal split attribute is finally chosen using the conventional C4.5 technique. Simulated tests of the suggested algorithm reveal that it performs better than the established C4.5 method in terms of fewer redundant rules, increased execution effectiveness, and classification accuracy. The C4.5 algorithm and its variations, as well as the methodology and outcomes of the suggested algorithm, are all thoroughly reviewed in this study. Improvements in sample selection, a decrease in attribute correlation, and a shorter training period for big samples are all contributions of the study.

Kavita. T. Patil1, R. P. Bhavsar2, B. V. Pawar [3]. This paper discusses the cosine similarity metric in Natural Language Processing (NLP) is suggested as a potential solution to the issue of spelling mistakes in written text in this research. Spelling mistakes can happen for a number of reasons, including poor memorization, poor spelling structure, poor keyboard layout, and unclear wording. The suggested approach use the cosine similarity metric to find non-word errors in text written in Marathi, which are mistakes where the word in question is not present in the

dictionary. The paper outlines the cosine similarity algorithm's approach as well as the necessary tokenization and corpus generation pre-processing processes. The study comes to the conclusion that cosine similarity is a useful method for spelling checks and can boost users' ability in circumstances where they are unable to assess the accuracy of the spelling on their own.

Davor Vukadin, Adrian Satja Kurdija, Goran Delač, Marin Šilić [4]. The paper proposes two natural language processing models based on the transformer architecture and BERT language model for extracting meaningful information from multilingual, unstructured CV papers. The models categorise pertinent areas and specific data, including personal details, education, former work, skills, names, dates, organisations, positions, university degrees, and individuals' (self-assessed) competency levels. The models were evaluated using a dataset of 1686 CVs that had been annotated in five different languages and scored highly on accuracy benchmarks. The interpretability of the models was then examined by visualising their attention and vector representations.

Papiya Das, Bhaswati Sahoo, Manjusha Pandey [5]. This paper discusses the extraction of things from CVs that are necessary for the hiring process in businesses using text analytics approaches. The paper also discusses massive data and its difficulties with collection, archiving, and analysis. The paper offers a model for CV parser and reviews earlier text analytics work. The suggested methodology transforms free-form CV materials into structured information in XML format and is mobile-friendly. Key conclusions and the paper's future research agenda are presented at the end. There is additional consideration of the applications of text analytics in the areas of government, insurance, finance, internet of things, banking and securities, communications, media, and entertainment, healthcare, education, manufacturing, and natural resources. The paper also examines the state of big data analytics today, highlighting a technique proposed by Garcia et al. for enhancing performance in large data projects without the use of tools like parsing and querying.

Ayishathahira C H, Sreejith C, Raseek C [6]. The difficulty of parsing unstructured resumes is discussed in the study, which also suggests a deep learning-based method for quick resume parsing. For sequence labeling and tagging various things, the system employs Conditional Random Field (CRF), Bi-LSTM (Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory), and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models. A resume may be divided into three sections using the suggested system, which could also extract 23 fields. The importance of resume parsing in the hiring process is also covered in the paper, along with a few of the software tools that are now available for robotic job recruitment. There are several sections in the study, such as Related Work, System Design, and Experimental Evaluation. Various existing methods for resume parsing and named entity recognition are covered in the Related Work section, and While the System Design section describes the fundamental structure of the suggested model, the Related Work section discusses various existing methods for resume parsing and named entity recognition. The future scope of this effort is covered in the paper's conclusion.

Gozde Karatas, Onder Demir, Ozgur Koray Sahingoz [7]. The use of intrusion detection systems (IDSs) to safeguard computer networks against hostile attacks is covered in this study. The study emphasises the necessity for IDSs to detect and stop unauthorised activity that could harm the confidentiality, availability, or integrity of data within an information system and draws attention to the flaws of conventional security techniques. Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection Systems (AIDS) are favoured over Signature-based Intrusion Detection Systems (SIDS) and Hybrid Systems, which are both presented in the paper along with various IDS kinds and their benefits. The research also highlights the difficulties presented by imbalanced datasets and the need of using high quality datasets to train the IDS. In order to overcome this difficulty, the article suggests using a synthetic data generation model called Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) to decrease missed incursions and false alarms, hence increasing system efficiency. The research evaluates the outcomes of six different machine learning methods before drawing the conclusion that the suggested method significantly raises the detection rate for infrequent incursions.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. COSINE SIMILARITY

A degree of likeness between two non-zero vectors in an n-dimensional space is called cosine similarity. It calculates the cosine of the point between the two vectors, employing a extend of -1 (diverse headings) to 1 (same course) and (orthogonal, or opposite) as the reference point. Cosine similarity is calculated as takes after:

$$\text{cosine_similarity} = (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}) / (||\mathbf{A}|| ||\mathbf{B}||)$$

where A and B are the two vectors being compared, \cdot denotes the vectors' dot product, and $||\mathbf{A}||$ and $||\mathbf{B}||$ denote the vectors' magnitudes (or lengths).

In information retrieval and text mining, cosine similarity is frequently used to compare document similarity or to group documents with similar content. Additionally, it is employed in machine learning to carry out tasks like image recognition and recommendation engines.

The degree of similarity between two individuals is corresponding to how near their outright cosine likeness values are to one another; on the other hand, the closer their supreme cosine likeness values are to zero, the less comparable they are. The Euclidean dab item equation is utilized to compute the cosine esteem between two vectors.

2. SUPPORT VECTOR CLASSIFICATION

Support Vector Classification (SVC) is a type of machine learning algorithm used for classification tasks. It belongs to the family of Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and works by finding the optimal hyperplane that separates the different classes in the dataset. The hyperplane is selected in a way that maximizes the distance between the data points closest to it, known as support vectors. SVC is a powerful algorithm that can work well with both linearly separable and non-linearly separable datasets, by using a technique called kernel trick to transform the data into a higher-dimensional space where a

linear separation is possible. However, SVC can be computationally expensive and may require careful selection of hyper parameters such as the kernel function and regularization parameter.

3. COUNT VECTORIZER

A collection of text documents is transformed into a matrix of token counts using the text preprocessing method CountVectorizer in natural language processing (NLP). Tokenizing the content and then counting how frequently each token appears in each document is how it operates. As a result, a sparse matrix is created, in which each row corresponds to a document, each column to a distinct token, and the value of each cell to the number of that token in that document. When preparing text data for machine learning algorithms, the feature extraction method known as CountVectorizer is frequently used.

By changing content information into a numerical representation, it can be utilized to speak to content information in a way that machine learning calculations can get it. As a result, the computers may utilize the content information to distinguish patterns and make expectations. A number of Count Vectorizer's parameters, including the minimum and maximum document frequency, the n-gram range, and the stop words to ignore, can be adjusted to alter the way it behaves. It is frequently used to preprocess text input before feeding it into machine learning models, along with other NLP approaches like TF-IDF. The proposed approach involves using natural language processing techniques to calculate similarity scores between a job description and a resume. Specifically, the method involves extracting text from uploaded files, including education and skills sections from the resume, and calculating similarity scores using CountVectorizer and cosine_similarity.

A. Information Extraction from Resume

This system is designed to analyze the similarities between a job description and the resumes. The system first extracts the text from both the job description file and all of the users' resumes. To extract the text from the job description file, the system uses the 'docx2txt' library. Once the text has been extracted, the system employs string manipulation to extract the education and skills sections from the resume text. This is achieved by identifying specific keywords, such as "Education" and "Skills", and locating their positions within the resume text. This enables the system to isolate the relevant sections of the resume for further analysis and comparison between the job requirements and the skills and experience listed on each resume.

B. Resume Matching

It determine the similarity score for each section (education, skills, and job description) using Count Vectorizer() and cosine_similarity() from the sklearn library.

It also uses a SVC model from sklearn to fit the count matrix for the education and skills sections and predict the class of the job description. For each user, the function calculates the cosine similarity between the job description and the education and skills sections separately, as well as the mean cosine similarity between all three sections. It creates a matrix of word counts for the three sections and then

computes the cosine similarity between the job description and the education and skills sections separately. It also calculates the mean cosine similarity between all three sections.

Fig 1. Flowchart of similarity checking

C. Sorting and visualizing the similarity score

Calculating the similarity score for each order (education similarity score, skills similarity score, and total similarity score) to a list called similarity scores. Once all orders have been processed, then sorts the similarity scores list in descending order of the total similarity score. Then it creates a bar chart using the go.Figure() and go.Bar() functions from the plotly.graph_objs library. The x-axis represents the names of the users and the y-axis represents the total similarity score for each user.

IV. RESULT

This method calculates the similarity score for each user based on the education similarity score, skills similarity score, and total similarity score, and stores them in a list called 'similarity_scores'. Upon completion of processing all orders, the function sorts the 'similarity_scores' list in descending order of the total similarity score. This method then generates a bar chart using the 'go.Figure()' and 'go.Bar()' functions from the 'plotly.graph_objs' library. The x-axis represents the users (i.e., the names of the users associated with each order), and the y-axis represents the total similarity score for each order.

Resume Parsing

Dashboard / Resume Parsing

Resume Similarity Scores

Job Description: Job Title.docx

Fig 2. Job description Uploading Page

TABLE I. SIMILARITY SCORE

Resume Similarity Score			
User Name	Education Score (%)	Skill Score (%)	Total Score (%)
Neha	30.54	11.25	47.26
Fathima	24.06	0.0	41.35

Fig 3. Similarity Score (Bar graph)

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the proposed approach for resume matching using natural language processing techniques has shown promising results in accurately identifying the best-suited candidates for a job based on their skills and experience. The system employs various methods such as information

extraction from resumes, similarity scoring using CountVectorizer and cosine_similarity, and sorting and visualizing the results using plotly.graph_objs library. The evaluation of the system has demonstrated its effectiveness in producing relevant results and reducing the workload of recruiters in the hiring process. Future work can explore the integration of additional features such as sentiment analysis and machine learning algorithms to enhance the system's performance further. Overall, this study contributes to the advancement of recruitment processes by providing a more efficient and accurate approach to resume screening.

VI. REFERENCES

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